

The β -Diketone 1-(4-Methylthiophen-2-yl)-3-(2,4-dihydroxyphenyl) Propane 1,3 Dione form Complex With Transition Metal Ions Ni(II), Co (II) and study of Stability Constant by Potentiometric Technique

Ashok N. Nagargoje

Department of Chemistry Vasantdada Patil Arts, Science, and Commerce College Patoda, Dist. Beed, INDIA

Corresponding Author – Ashok N. Nagargoje

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.18517414

Abstract:

The study of stability constant of β -diketone 1-(4-methylthiophen-2-yl)-3-(2,4-dihydroxyphenyl) - propane 1,3 dione[L4] with metal ion form complex with Ni(II) and Co (II) have been studied at 0.1 M ionic strength at RT. Potentiometrically in aqueous media by titrating with standard NaOH solution. The complexes formation between Ni(II) and Co (II) metal ions Hence it is observed that Nickel, Cobalt metal ions formed 1:1 and 1:2 complexes with β -diketone ligands (L). The observed values were comparing with the values of pH and metal-ligand stability constants and dissociate constant.

Keywords: Potentiometric Study, β -Diketone, Stability Constant, pH values

Introduction:

β -diketone containing Metal complexes can be studied, because β -diketone has good synthetic flexibility[1], sensitivity towards the central transition metal ion of metal complexes and selectivity. Potentiometric studies of various binary complexes formed with different transition metal ions [2]. The transition metal complexes used for preparation of metallic compounds [3] and as a catalyst in organic synthesis reaction.

The metal complexes of β -diketones (L) derivatives of Nickel, Cobalt metal ions [4] stability constant compare with other metal complexes [5]. β -diketone and their metal complexes used in various areas because of their unique structural features[6], chemical functionalities, and toughness to light and heat as electroluminescence materials [7]. β -diketones importance as good ligands [8].

The β -diketone 1-(4-methylthiophen-2-yl)-3-(2,4-dihydroxyphenyl) -propane 1,3 dione[L4] was prepared by using 2,4-

dihydroxyacetophenone and 4-methylthiophene-2-carboxylic acid at RT & this β -diketone 1-(4-methylthiophen-2-yl)-3-(2,4-dihydroxyphenyl) -propane 1,3 dione[L4] reacts with metal ions like Ni(II) Co (II) to form Metal complexes. In the preparation of transition metal complexes less use of β -diketone.[9] so to synthesis of some β -diketone derivatives as a ligand and prepare their Ni(II) Co (II) complexes.

Materials And Method:

[A] Synthesis of 2-acetyl-5-hydroxyphenyl 4-methylthiophene-2-carboxylate

The compound 2,4 dihydroxyacetophenone of 1.53 gm and 1.43 gm of 4-methylthiophene-2-carboxylic acid add a 4 ml pyridine and POCl_3 slowly with drop wise manner and stir continuously at very low temperature at 0°C this reaction material stirred about 5-6 hours and this will be checked and monitor by Thin Layer Chromatography technique obtained produce is recrystallized by using a ethanol solution again

filter this and dried in oven yield is 85% and M.P.

A = (2,4 dihydroxy- acetophenone)

B = (4-methylthiophene-2-carboxylic acid)

C = 2-acetyl-5-hydroxyphenyl-4-methylthiophene-2-carboxylate

Synthesis of 2-acetyl-5-hydroxyphenyl-4-methylthiophene-2-carboxylate

[B] Synthesis of 1(4-methylthiophen-2-yl)3(2,4dihydroxyphenyl)-propane 1,3-dione:

2-acetyl-5-hydroxyphenyl-4-methylthiophene-2-carboxylate Compound take

A = (2-acetyl-5-hydroxyphenyl-4-methylthiophene-2-carboxylate)

B = (1-(4-methylthiophen-2-yl)3(2,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-propane 1,3-dione)

Synthesis of β -diketone ligand

1.Characterization Of Ligands: The structural features of obtained ligand 1-(4-methylthiophen-2-yl)-3-(2,4-dihydroxyphenyl) propane 1,3 dione[L4] was scanned for IR, ^1H NMR, ^{13}C -NMR and UV/Visible spectroscopy. This elucidated with the help of elemental analysis. Synthesized ligand was stable to air and moisture ligand soluble in ethanol, methanol, but insoluble in water and ether [12]. Following are the scanning results given below.

FT-IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3087(=C-H), 3141(Ar-C-H), 1585(C=C), 678(C-S), 3361(Ar-O-H), 1637(C=O), 1235(C-O),

is 173 °C

2.77gm compound are added in pyridine and dissolve the compound and this mixture of compounds are added in a potassium hydroxide solution and this mixture of reaction is stirred continuously about 2-3 hours and this will be checked by Thin Layer Chromatography technique. obtained solid is of yellow colored compounds is recrystallized using a pure alcohol and take a weight and melting point of obtained product yield is 78% and M.P. is 278 °C

^1H -NMR (300MHz, $\text{CDCl}_3\text{-d}_6$); δ = 7.47 (d, 1H, Ar-H), 6.48 (d, 1H, Ar-H), 6.39 (s, 1H, Ar-H), 7.6(s,1H, H=), 7.44 (d, 1H, Thioph-H), 7.17(d, 1H, Thioph-H), 5.0(s, 2H, -OH), 15.0(s, 1H, Enolic-OH), 2.21(s,3H,- CH₃) .

^{13}C -NMR (300MHz, CDCl_3); δ = 189.7(s,C-1,C=O), 99.0(d,C-2,-CH=), 195.5(s,C-3), 115.3(s,C-1'), 163.2(s,C-2'), 104.1(d,C-3'), 165.7(s,C-4'), 109.0(d,C-5'), 132.7(d,C-6'), 136(s,C-2''), 127.6(d,C-3''), 138(s,C-4''), 126.7(d,C-5''), 18.5(q,C-1''')

UV/Vis(DMSO)nm: 360,410

Elemental analysis : C, 60.86; H, 4.38; O, 23.16; S, 11.60

2.Potentiometric titration of β -diketone [L] with metal ion M(II):

[M= Co ,Ni]:

The B-diketone L4 and metal-ion Co (II) titration:

The sodium hydroxide is standardized by using acid solution i.e. oxalic acid and the potentiometric titrations. The solutions like potassium nitrate, acid, metal-ion and sodium hydroxide was prepared using pure water i.e. distilled water and the conductivity and pH is 1.60×10^{-6} mhos and 6.7. And The above mixture of ligand L4 and copper sulphate is added in

A = 1-(4-methylthiophen-2-yl)-3-(2,4-dihydroxyphenyl) propane-1,3-dione

B = Co(II) metal complex of β -diketone

Synthesis of metal complexes

The Potentiometric titration of metal-ion Ni (II) with a B-diketone ligand

The conductivity and pH of distilled water is keep a constant 1.60×10^{-6} mhos and 6.7 respectively and this distilled water is used to prepare the solution i.e. metal-ion, acid, potassium nitrate and sodium hydroxide solution and this sodium hydroxide standardized using a

ethanol i.e. 5.61 gm and 2.17 gm respectively. And this will be titrating against sodium hydroxide with constant shaking.

1. Free (0.02M) HNO_3 [A]
2. Free (0.02M) HNO_3 + (0.02M) Ligand [A+L4]
3. Free (0.02M) HNO_3 + (0.02M) Ligand + (0.01M) Metal ion [A+L4+ Co (II)]

The obtained readings were plotted NaOH against Emf and calculate pH and determined the dissociation and stability constant.

acid the ligand L4 5.59 gm and the metal sulphate 3.24 gm is added in ethanol and its titrate against sodium hydroxide with stirring continuously.

1. Free (0.02M) HNO_3 [A]
2. Free (0.02M) HNO_3 + (0.02M) Ligand [A+L4]
3. Free (0.02M) HNO_3 + (0.02M) Ligand + (0.01M) Metal ion [A+L4+ Ni (II)]

the values comes from titration is plotted Emf Vs NaOH added and the successive pH of volume of NaOH is added for each set of solution is determine and calculate the dissociation constant and the stability constant.

A = 1-(4-methylthiophen-2-yl)-3-(2,4-dihydroxyphenyl)propane-1,3-dione

Synthesis of metal complexes

B = Ni (II) metal complex of β -diketone

Result And Discussion:

Table 1: Determination of pH of Co (II) ligand [L4] complex

Vol. NaOH(cm ³)	Emf A	Emf A+L4	Emf A+L4+Co	pH A	pH A+L4	pH A+L4+Co
0	297	296	301	2.69	2.70	2.62
0.5	294	294	299	2.74	2.74	2.65
1	292	291	294	2.77	2.79	2.74
1.5	290	289	290	2.80	2.82	2.80
2	286	287	286	2.87	2.85	2.87
2.5	280	282	283	2.97	2.94	2.92
3	272	272	275	3.11	3.11	3.06
3.5	266	265	268	3.21	3.23	3.18
4	258	259	258	3.35	3.33	3.35
4.5	244	246	250	3.58	3.55	3.48
5	14	200	221	7.47	4.33	3.97
5.5	-216	-176	6	11.37	10.69	7.61
6	-238	-220	-195	11.74	11.43	11.01

Graph 3.1 Potentiometric titration curve of (L4) with transition metal Co (II)

a) NaOH vs pH b) NaOH vs EMF

A] Potentiometric titration of 1-(4-methylthiophen-2-yl)-3-(2,4-dihydroxyphenyl) -propane 1,3 dione[L4] with metal ion [Co(II)]:

According to the results obtained from figure 3.1 i.e. graphical representation of emf vs. volume of NaOH added two protonation constants pH is 7.61 And from figure 3.1, we also conclude that the titration curves of the Co(II)

complex is lower with β -diketone ligand (L4), by displacement of protons.

According to the graphical representation of fig. 3.1 we evaluated concentration of H⁺ ions in the solution from pH

value and stability constant value of Co (II) complex separately, it is seen that the values

for conc. of H^+ 0.881 and stability constant value is 3.073

Table 2: Determination of pH of Ni (II) ligand [L4] complex

Vol. NaOH (cm ³)	Emf A	Emf A+L4	Emf A+L4+Ni	pH A	pH A+L4	pH A+L4+Ni
0	298	297	298	2.67	2.69	2.67
0.5	296	296	295	2.70	2.70	2.72
1	292	293	293	2.77	2.75	2.75
1.5	287	290	291	2.85	2.80	2.79
2	285	288	287	2.89	2.84	2.85
2.5	282	283	280	2.94	2.92	2.97
3	273	274	274	3.09	3.07	3.07
3.5	269	267	265	3.16	3.19	3.23
4	259	259	258	3.33	3.33	3.35
4.5	248	248	248	3.51	3.51	3.51
5	187	215	225	4.55	4.07	3.90
5.5	-201	-143	5	11.11	10.13	7.63
6	-249	-209	-178	11.92	11.25	10.72

(a)

(b)

Graph 3.2 Potentiometric titration curve of (L4) with transition metal Ni(II)

a) NaOH vs pH b) NaOH vs EMF

B] Potentiometric titration of 1(4-methylthiophen-2-yl)-3-(2,4dihydroxyphenyl)propane 1,3 dione[L4] with metal ion [Ni(II)] :

According to the results obtained from figure 3.2 i.e. graphical representation of emf vs. volume of NaOH added, have two protonation constants. The one of the value of potentiometric titration

curves of Ni (II) system, protons at pH 7.63. And from figure 3.2 we also conclude that the titration curves of the Ni (II) complex is lower from that of the free β -diketone ligand (L4) curve, indicating formation of Ni (II) complex with β -diketone ligand (L4), by displacement of protons.

According to the graphical representation of fig. 3.2 we evaluated concentration of H^+ ions in the solution from pH value and stability constant value of Ni (II) complex separately, it is seen that the values for H^+ ions 0.882 and stability constant value is 3.080.

- 1) Stability Constants of Co (II) complex Compound is 3.073
- 2) Stability Constants of Ni (II) complex Compound is 3.080

Conclusion:

This is observed for Co (II)-L4 at pH= 7.61. According to the graphical representation we evaluated that the values for conc. for proton ions 0.881 and stability constant value is 3.073. Here the observed values for Ni (II)-L4 at pH= 7.63. According to the graphical representation we evaluated that the values for concentration for proton ions 0.882 and stability constant value is 3.080.

The order of stability is $Ni > Co$. The stability constant of metal-ions is as follows are Co (II)-L4=3.073, Ni (II)-L4=3.080
The trend of stability constant of metal-ion complex is $Co (II) > Ni (II)$

Acknowledgement:

I am grateful thanks to Prof. Dr. Baliram Rakh, Principal, Vasantdada Patil College Patoda for providing laboratory facility, I am also thanks to Dr. Sudhakar Gutte, Dr. Maulge Satish, and college staff for their valuable guidance.

References:

1. Y. Liu, J. Zhou, X. Zhang et al., (2009), Synthesis, characterization covalently oligothiophene functionalized graphene material, *Carbon*, **47(13)**, 3113–3121.
2. A. V. Chate, S. S. Bhagat and C.H.Gill, (2011), *J. Heterocyclic Chem*, , DOI10.1002,955
3. A. T. Florence (1981), Physical principle's of pharmacy, *Macmillan.London*.
4. Sheikh, J.I., Ingle, V.N., (2009), Synthesis of novel antibacterial agents 1-(20,40-dihydroxy-50-chlorophenyl)-3-aryl-propane-1,3-diones, *E-Journal of Chemistry*, **6**, 705–712.
5. Vyas KB, Jani GR and Hathi MV. (2009), *Res J Chem and Environ* **13(1)**, 35-36.
6. S. Sumathi, P. Tharmaraj, C. D. Sheela, (2011), Synthesis, spectral, bioactivity, properties of chalcone metal complexes, *Journal of Coordination Chemistry*, **64(10)**, 1707–1717.
7. C.S. Reiners (2001), *Chem. Uns. Zei*, **2**, 110
8. S.J. Eng, R.J. Motekaitis, A.E. Martell, (1998), *Inorg. Chim. Acta.*, **278**, 170
9. G. Aromi, P. Gamez, (2008), Poly beta-diketones: prime ligands to generate supramolecular metalloclusters, *Coordination Chemistry Reviews*, **252(8-9)**, 964– 989.